

Implementation of a Mobility Protocol on a Medical-Surgical Unit

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Background

- Falls among older adult patients in the hospital setting are one of the most critical issues in health care today (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2015).
- Over 150,000 falls lead to injury in the United States (Institute for Healthcare Improvement [IHI], 2018).
- One of the Joint Commission's Hospital National Patient Safety Goals for 2018 is to decrease falls since they account for a significant share of injuries among hospitalized patients.

Problem Statement

- Nurse-driven mobility protocols increase the chance a patient will ambulate within the first three days of hospitalization in the ICU and acute care setting (Gruet et al., 2013).
- There is little research on implementation of an early mobility protocol for patients in medical-surgical units. It is important to direct some of the early mobilization protocols to this population.

Purpose Statement

- The purpose of this DNP project was to implement an evidence-based mobility protocol on a medical-surgical unit to improve patient outcomes by decreasing falls in older adults at a hospital in Southern California.

Limitations

- Small sample size limited generalizability
- Infrequent fall occurrence prior to project start

Supporting Framework

Methods

- Conducted a quality improvement project in a large academic teaching hospital
- Developed a pre-post project design to collect and evaluate data
- Consulted with members of the interprofessional team including frontline staff members, the nurse manager of the project unit, the chief nursing officer, the chief executive officer, the inpatient medical director, and the physical therapy department educator
- Modified existing ICU mobility protocol to meet medical-surgical population
- Targeted patients 65 years or older who were recipients of the early mobility protocol interventions
- Administered surveys to assess nursing staff knowledge and attitude about patient falls and mobility
- Developed and provided a 30-minute educational session for the project unit nursing staff and physical therapy department staff to introduce the early mobility protocol

Results

Mobility Protocol Tool

Unanticipated Findings

- Electronic Medical Record (EMR) documentation not standardized
- Standardized EMR mobility report did not capture information as intended
- Multiple patient mobility orders due to reconciliation process
- High patient acuity limited use of protocol
- Decreases in the number of nursing aides available limited full implementation of the protocol

Recommendations

- Adapt and implement the nursing mobility protocol for all medical-surgical units
- Standardize and define mobility documentation requirements in EMR
- Include patient mobility in new hire orientation
- Monitor and share mobility activity status results with frontline staff, the multidisciplinary team, and leadership